

Enhanced Taxonomy with Physical-Digital-Infrastructure (PDI) for extended ODD definition applied to Connected and Cooperative Automated mobility (CCAM)

Secil Ercan¹, and Dominique Gruyer², and Abdelmenname Hedhli¹, and Sio-Song Ieng², and Léo Mendiboure¹,

Abstract—The Operational Design Domain (ODD) is a key concept for future Automated Driving Systems (ADS) and Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM). Indeed, it defines the conditions (speed, type of road, weather, etc.) and operating space under which ADS are likely to operate safely, depending on their characteristics, dynamics, and capacities: type of vehicle, level of automation, acceleration and braking limits, tire grip capacity etc. Work in this area is therefore crucial to enable ADS and CCAM to become a reality. That is why, we propose a new enhanced taxonomy for ADS. It addresses key aspects including ODD, Environment Description (ED), Object and Event Detection and Response (OEDR), and Testing scenarios (SCEN) to create a precise and flexible taxonomy. Moreover, it aims at aligning the Physical, Digital, and Communication Infrastructure (PDI) Library with the proposed taxonomy to improve CCAM system. Finally, it is applied to a specific use case dedicated to Road workers in the field (RWiF) to demonstrate its relevance, efficiency, and ease of implementation.

Taxonomy, ODD, PDI, CAV, CCAM.

I. INTRODUCTION

Automated vehicles will play an important role in future transport systems. There are many benefits associated with their deployment, including enhanced road safety, optimized transport flows and reduced energy consumption [1]. Their adoption will require the development of a range of services, in particular Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM), which will guarantee the safe operation interaction of automated vehicles with their environment. Such CCAM will be necessary whatever the level of autonomy targeted for Automated Driving Systems (ADS): Level 1 (Driver Assistance), Level 2 (Partial Driving Automation), Level 3 (Conditional Driving Automation), Level 4 (High Driving Automation), and Level 5 (Full Driving Automation) [2].

*This work is supported by Horizon Europe program in the framework of AUGMENTED CCAM and BPI in the framework of PRISSMA project (French Great AI Challenges)

¹Secil Ercan, COSYS/ERENA, Université Gustave Eiffel, Bordeaux, France secil.ercan@univ-eiffel.fr

²Dominique Gruyer, COSYS/PICS-L, Université Gustave Eiffel, F-77454 Marne-la-Vallée, France dominique.gruyer@univ-eiffel.fr

¹Abdelmenname Hedhli, COSYS/ERENA, Université Gustave Eiffel, Bordeaux, France abdelmenname.hedhli@univ-eiffel.fr

²Sio-Song Ieng, COSYS/PICS-L, Université Gustave Eiffel, F-77454 Marne-la-Vallée, France sio-song.ieng@univ-eiffel.fr

¹Léo Mendiboure, COSYS/ERENA, Université Gustave Eiffel, Bordeaux, France leo.mendiboure@univ-eiffel.fr

An important concept associated with the implementation of these ADSs and CCAMs is the Operational Design Domain (ODD) [3], which aims to define the conditions (type of road, speed, weather, etc.) where an ADS is expected to operate safely, depending on its various characteristics: type of vehicle, level of automation (3 and 4 are most concerned by ODD), sensors available, communication capability, etc. To specify the ODD, various solutions can be adopted, but the most common is to define an ODD taxonomy that can be used by the various players involved in the implementation and supervision of automated and connected vehicles [4]: vehicle manufacturer, public authority, highway operator, etc.

Various taxonomies have been proposed in the literature to date. However, we believe it is important to extend this research effort to real-life cases and to actual implementation in use cases that could have an impact on the taxonomy definition itself. That is why this paper presents a comprehensive work focused on the development of an enhanced taxonomy for Automated Driving Systems (ADS), extending a conceptual solution we proposed in [4]. The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- The definition of an enhanced taxonomy addressing mainly the key aspects for Operational Design Domain (ODD) and Environment Description (ED), useful for downstream functions such as Object and Event Detection and Response (OEDR), and Testing scenarios (SCEN). The current work allows to create a precise and unified taxonomy that accurately describes the real-world intricacies, tailored to specific activities;
- The integration of elements in the taxonomy aiming at considering the Physical, Digital, and Communication Infrastructure (PDI) [5] Library and components in ODD definition (extended ODD) for the CCAM systems development, implementation, and deployment.
- The implementation of an improved category dedicated to ego-vehicle features and capabilities;
- The application of the newly defined taxonomy to a specific and real-world use case: Road Workers in the Field (RWiF);
- The discussion about considerations of specific requirements for dynamic, adaptive, and incremental improvements over time for extended ODD capabilities.

The paper is organized into six sections, covering intro-

duction, literature review with existing taxonomies overview, proposed new taxonomy focusing on PDI and ego-vehicle, application of the proposed taxonomy on a specific use case to define ODD descriptors/scenes/scenario, discussion about extended ODD considering dynamic conditions, and conclusion. Each section serves a distinct purpose, providing a systematic analysis of existing taxonomies, defining a new taxonomy, and demonstrating practical applications within the context of CCAM systems.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND EXISTING TAXONOMY

A. Methodology

In the realm of taxonomy analysis for autonomous vehicles, this article outlines a systematic approach in its bibliographic methodology section. The investigation encompasses diverse taxonomies found in the literature, classifying them into four main document types: standard-related documents proposed by standardization bodies, institutional-related documents from government agencies, particularly technical reports, research-related documents from researchers and research labs, primarily in conference and journal papers, and working group-related documents from international working groups, primarily in technical reports. The taxonomy structure employed for analysis follows a three-tiered tree structure, comprising components (e.g., Physical Infrastructure), subcategories (e.g., Roadway Types), and elements (e.g., One lane). A reading template was devised and applied consistently across documents to ensure a cohesive analysis. This template includes criteria such as reference paper details, document category classification, the definition of Operational Design Domain (ODD), keywords for thematic specification, comments for document-specific elements, and the tree classification of ODD attributes. This rigorous methodology serves as a foundation for comprehensively reviewing and synthesizing existing state-of-the-art taxonomies in the field of autonomous vehicles.

B. Literature review

The methodology used to identify and analyse the different taxonomies proposed in the literature is presented in this paper.

The British Standards Institution (BSI) proposed a taxonomy to specify ODD [6] that provided a minimal hierarchy including scenery, environmental conditions, and dynamic elements. Connectivity related elements were also given in the environmental conditions. However, dynamic elements mainly consider other traffic elements, while the subject vehicle is only concerned with its speed. Several works have constructed their taxonomies on the taxonomy presented in this standard.

Institutional based documents, mainly technical reports published by government agencies, proposed taxonomies to carry out in ADS projects. The Korea Institute Of Intelligent Transport Systems [7] introduced the taxonomy with geometry factors, operational factors, and environmental factors. This definition does not include the categories related to

digital infrastructure and subject vehicle. U.S. Department of Transportation, National Highway Traffic Safety Administration [8] defined a taxonomy including physical infrastructure, zones, environmental conditions, objects, operational conditions, and connectivity, but not any categories for the subject vehicle. The taxonomy of U.S. Department of Transportation, Federal Highway Administration [9] mainly presented three categories: roadway, environment, and objects.

As well as the standard or institutional related documents, research papers proposing taxonomies are further analysed. Scholtes et al. [10] described different layers, namely road network and traffic guidance objects, roadside structures, dynamic objects, environmental conditions, digital information. This broad description does not still include the subject vehicle. Similarly, Bagschik et al. [11] presented their model with the layers as road level, traffic infrastructure, objects, environment. The taxonomy of Chen and Khou [12] included highway ontology, weather ontology, and vehicle ontology. Vreeswijk et al. [13] introduced a conceptual structure including scene, physical infrastructure, geofenced areas, situational/environmental conditions, digital infrastructure, vehicle automation capabilities, operational performance. This structure does not, however, detail them with hierarchical sub elements and does not include other traffic users. In [14], the layers were defined as limitations on road environment, vehicle behaviour, vehicle state. These limitations do not take into account digital infrastructure and other users. Pfeil et al. [15] proposed a taxonomy not only consisting of functional constraints, environment, system-internal conditions, but also their combinations. Erz et al. [16] developed their taxonomy based on the categories in [6]: scenery, environmental conditions, dynamic elements. Kim et al. [17] implemented their scenario on a pre-defined taxonomy including roadway related features and scenery, environmental conditions and connectivity, dynamic elements, subject vehicle with limited features such as maximum speed, weight, etc. Ruchiga et al. [18] proposed an ontology for ODD with three main classes: scenery, dynamic elements, and environment. This ontology also includes a human and autonomous vehicle driving styles, but not digital infrastructures. Gyllenhammar et al. [19] defined several categories for operating conditions: dynamic elements, scenery, connectivity, actions&events (other actors), goals&values (permanent and transient), functional range, fallback ready user.

International Working Groups (WG) also proposed taxonomies for ODD in the technical reports. The taxonomy of Groupe PSA [20] consisted of road, visibility, and traffic. European Global Navigation Satellite Systems Agency (GSA) [21] divided the taxonomy into three categories: scenery, environmental conditions, and dynamic elements. These categories include sub elements for connectivity and the subject vehicle, even if they are limited. Association for Standardization of Automation and Measuring Systems (ASAM) [22] defined three classes: locatable object (traffic participant and non-traffic participant) and ambient object (road network topology and environment), traffic participant flow. They used the taxonomy defined in [6] while describing

their methodologies for ODD language.

Mendiboure et al. [4], which is the previous version of this current article, proposed a taxonomy and applied it in a use case, namely bus station automated service (BuSAS). This taxonomy includes six main categories: physical infrastructure, scenery, environmental conditions, traffic conditions, digital infrastructure, and vehicle capabilities. The main contributions to the taxonomy of this work will be on the digital infrastructure and vehicle features. Moreover, small modifications on the physical infrastructure and scenery will also be done.

Table I compares the different taxonomies based on six categories, i.e. physical infrastructure, scenery, environmental conditions, traffic conditions, digital infrastructure, and vehicle features. These categories will be detailed with the proposed taxonomy in Section III. According to this comparison, physical infrastructure and environmental conditions are commonly used in taxonomies where scenery and traffic conditions are considered not in all works, but in many others. Nevertheless, the least considered categories are digital infrastructure and vehicle features. Some works already defined elements related to connectivity, but they do not include several information relating to digital infrastructure; these works are marked "Partial". Similarly, works that presented the subject vehicles with only in terms of their speed and/or maneuvering capacities, without taking automation-related features into account, are marked "Partial" in the vehicle features category.

Ref.	PI	S	EC	TC	DI	VF
[6]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partial	Partial
[7]	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
[8]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
[9]	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Partial	No
[10]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
[11]	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
[12]	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Partial
[13]	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
[14]	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
[15]	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Partial
[16]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partial	Partial
[17]	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Partial	Partial
[18]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
[19]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partial	Partial
[20]	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
[21]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partial	Partial
[22]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Partial
[4]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partial	Partial
Proposed	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

PI: Physical Infrastructure, S: Scenery, EC: Environmental Conditions, TC: Traffic Conditions, DI: Digital Infrastructure, VF: Vehicle Features

TABLE I

COMPARISON OF THE DIFFERENT EXISTING TAXONOMIES

III. PROPOSAL OF NEW TAXONOMY DEFINITION

In this section, we present the proposed taxonomy, synthesized from the comprehensive bibliographic exploration detailed in the previous sections. The operational design domain (ODD) serves as a critical aspect in driving automation systems, delineating the conditions under which

automated driving tasks are designed to operate. While Level 5 Automated Driving Systems (ADS) have no ODD limitations, Levels 3 and 4 may impose restrictions such as speed range, environmental conditions, and traffic conditions, necessitating ODD monitoring and facilitating a dynamic driving task (DDT) fallback upon ODD exit. The definition of ODD is pivotal, providing an unambiguous description of the external world within which ADS can execute DDT. This description, encompassing terms, scales, and quality, permeates ADS specification, design, validation, and operation phases, establishing it as a foundational milestone in the process. The development of a taxonomy for ODD terminology is fundamental, establishing a common language that empowers ADS manufacturers, users, operators, and regulators. This taxonomy aids in specifying and implementing safety requirements, referencing ODD attributes and performance requirements, and enhancing confidence in product safety through test and verification activities. Crucially, this taxonomy also harmonizes the description of ODD with the Environmental Description (ED), ensuring compatibility and relevance across activities. While ODD pertains to the system's capabilities under operating conditions, ED describes the actual world, reflecting the real operating conditions encountered by the vehicle. The taxonomy, shared by both domains, facilitates seamless proof of the operational domain's alignment with ODD capabilities. The taxonomy, developed based on an extensive review of academic, standard, institutional, and Work Group documents, provides a foundation for describing the real world precisely and unambiguously. Its structure allows incremental improvement and enrichment, presenting a versatile tool for defining both the operational area (ED) and the operational design domain (ODD), as outlined in this paper.

Below is the overall taxonomy derived from the literature review, which is presented as follows:

- Physical infrastructure - includes all the information related to the configuration, the state and the equipment of the physical infrastructure: Roadway type, roadway edge, roadway geometry, junctions, temporary structures, fixed surrounding structures, special structures and characteristics, signage, man-made landmark;
- Scenery - includes all the information related to the scene, going beyond the physical infrastructure: specific zones, region/states, geo-fencing, landmark;
- Environmental conditions - includes all information related to weather conditions, particulates, illumination, temperature, weather-induced roadway conditions, air humidity;
- Traffic conditions - includes all information related to traffic conditions: traffic density, road users, traffic safety;
- Digital infrastructure - includes all information related to digital infrastructure and connectivity (which are necessary to safely perform the dynamic driving task): type of information, radio access technology, service type, road side sensors, HD maps;

Fig. 1. 2-Layer Structure of the Proposed Taxonomy for ODD definition

Fig. 2. Ego-vehicle modelling with function and interaction with the environment layer

- Vehicle features - includes all information related to vehicle: Advanced Driver Assistance System (ADAS) features, dynamic vehicle capabilities (maximal/authorised speed, manoeuvres, tire state, etc.), and vehicle type and size.

Figure 1 displays the 2-layer structure of the proposed taxonomy.

A. Focus on PDI element within taxonomy

Focusing on PDI within the taxonomy, we propose to introduce new elements, particularly in digital and communication infrastructures, e.g. type and content of information, radio access technology, service type, road side sensors with their types and services, HD maps layers.

B. Focus on ego-vehicle feature category

In addition, we propose ADAS features as well as vehicle's dynamic capabilities and its type and size.

Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 demonstrate, respectively, the ego-vehicle modelling with function and interaction with the environment layer and the ego-vehicle HD maps with the different layers.

Fig. 3. Ego-vehicle HD map with the different layers

IV. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE NEW TAXONOMY ON SPECIFIC USE CASE (UC): RWiF

This section presents a practical application of taxonomy in shaping ODD descriptors and their subsequent integration into test scenarios, with a specific focus on the use case of Road Workers in the Field. The primary objective is to elucidate the seamless transition from taxonomy elements to ODD definition, emphasising the critical role of identifying PDIs. One of the objectives is to demonstrate how taxonomy elements actively contribute to ODD definition, emphasising the essential aspect of PDI identification. The chapter underscores the significance of incorporating the concept of PDIs during the ODD definition phase and integrating them into test scenarios. This approach not only adds depth to the ODD but also provides tangible evidence of the substantial impact of PDIs on its extension.

A. The use case Road Workers in the Field

This Use Case centres on addressing two critical aspects of Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs) navigating through road works. In the first part, the system provides a Road Works Warning (RWW) for CAVs by integrating planned road works information into the Traffic Management System (TMS). This includes details such as the work site's start/end position, duration, and speed limits for affected portions. The Road Side Unit (RSU) broadcasts Decentralised Environmental Notification Messages (DENM) and Map Extension Messages (MAPeM) to CAVs, conveying

Fig. 4. Use case Road Workers in the Field with PDI solutions where ego-vehicle approaching a work zone area

recommended paths and cones sequence positions. CAVs process this information and take appropriate actions when approaching road works area and going through it safely. The second part focuses on enhancing road worker safety by embedding an On-Board Unit (OBU) in a patrol vehicle within the work zone. The OBU assesses risk, computes a local HD Map, and monitors approaching connected vehicles' trajectories. It activates sound and visual alarms if a vehicle poses a danger to the road works site, contributing to an overall solution that aims to improve the safety and efficiency of CAVs in road work environments.

Fig. 4 shows the use case RWiF with recommended path. For the purposes of the Taxonomy \Rightarrow ODD \Rightarrow Scenario process outlined in this paper, the emphasis will be exclusively on Part 1 of this use case. This involves conveying recommended paths and cone positions to CAVs using an RSU through DENM and MAPeM. The focus is on how CAVs process this information and take appropriate actions to navigate road works safely.

The experimental phase for this use case comprises three stages: 1) open environment testing at the A63 ZEHNS site, 2) controlled environment testing at the Satory site near Versailles, and 3) simulation using a specific platform developed by University of Gustave Eiffel. Controlled environment and simulation tests are scheduled for September 2024, while open environment tests will occur in December 2024.

B. Presentation of the process

This process involves two key steps. In the initial step, we carefully select ODD descriptors and corresponding metrics from the taxonomy. It is crucial to tailor these selections specifically to our use case, which is Road Workers in the Field (RWiF). The precise targeting of relevant descriptors and metrics ensures a nuanced representation of the operational domain, facilitating the coherent definition of test scenarios. This focused approach enhances the clarity and precision of characterizing the ODD for the RWiF use case. It is important to note that not all ODD descriptors suggested by the taxonomy may be relevant. It is the specific use case that will determine which ODD descriptors are genuinely useful and which are not. In the illustration presented in the following paragraph (STEP 1 - From the Taxonomy to ODD descriptors), the ODD descriptors from the taxonomy considered useful are highlighted in red, while those deemed irrelevant are indicated in orange. Moving on to the second step, after the meticulous definition of the ODD using descriptors derived from the taxonomy, we utilize these descriptors to formulate the associated test scenarios. In essence,

descriptors extracted from the taxonomy—characterizing components, subcategories, and elements of the ODD—are systematically applied to construct situations and test conditions representative of the specified operational domain. This comprehensive approach allows for an in-depth evaluation of the autonomous system's performance and robustness across realistic and diverse contexts. It ensures thorough coverage of the features identified by the taxonomy, establishing a consistent correspondence between ODD descriptors and the practical situations tested. Ultimately, this methodology contributes to a rigorous validation of the autonomous system under real-world usage conditions.

C. From the taxonomy to the ODD descriptors

In the first step, the selected ODD descriptors from the proposed taxonomy will be presented. These descriptors are explained as follows:

- Physical infrastructure: Roadway type (divided roads, type of pavement surface, luminance of road surface, pavement grip coefficient, road marking cones), roadway geometry (width of the lane, radius of curvature), junctions (ramp in, ramp off, lane merging, lane addition), temporary structures (workzones), fixed surrounding structures (tunnel, GPS/GNSS disturbance zones, metal structure), and signage (road marking, zebra, boundary markers, dynamic signs, temporary signs).
- Scenery: Region/state (France with the French traffic rules and associated signage) and interference zones (tunnel).
- Environmental conditions: Weather (fog, rain, snow, ice, wind), particulates (dust and sand cloud, smoke, dust and sand), illumination (illumination level, conditions, and variations), temperature (low, high), weather-induced roadway conditions (road surface state).
- Traffic conditions: Traffic density (on the ego-vehicle traffic lane, opposite direction, ego-vehicle direction, ramp in, and ramp off) and road users (type of user and user speed on the mentioned lanes/directions).
- Digital infrastructure: Type of information (GPS signal, expected information by the vehicle and by the system), radio access technology (protocol V2I/I2V and technology features), service type (augmented CCAM services), road side sensors (type of sensors, type of service), and HD maps (layer 1, layer 3, layer 4, layer 5, layer 6).
- Vehicle features: ADAS features (level of automation, sensors, perception, decision making, path planning, communication), dynamic capabilities (speed, acceleration, maneuvers, tire state, braking system, steering capability), type and size (light car and vehicle width/length/height).

D. From ODD descriptors to scenes and scenario description

Once the ODD has been established, the process continues by defining test scenarios using various descriptors. To illustrate this process, we will present a scenario that incorporates

Fig. 5. One scene of the testing scenario for RWiF with ODD descriptors

Physical and Digital Infrastructures (PDI). The scenarios, as presented here, unfold as a sequence of different scenes. We will delve into the initial scenes of the scenario without necessarily presenting the entire scenario, as it may become complex and is not always necessary for our demonstration. Subsequently, we will focus on one of these scenes to recall the descriptors and metrics used, derived from the ODD. This approach solidifies the practical use of ODD descriptors in specific situations, thereby demonstrating their significance in the definition and evaluation of test scenarios.

Fig. 5 illustrates the initial scene with the ODD descriptors for the use case RWiF. This scene is located in France on a divided highway where there are two lanes (lanes 2 and 3) 3.5 m wide in the same direction as the CAV, and one shoulder lane (lane 1). The physical infrastructure descriptors specific to the RWiF use case are the work zone as a temporary structure with road marking cones (on lane 2) and a temporary sign for work zones. Environmental conditions are not specifically modified for this scenario, and are described as normal, with daylight for illumination conditions and normal road surface state. The descriptors for traffic conditions indicate that the road user type is conventional car on lane 3 and the traffic density is medium here.

For the ACCAM service road workers in the field, there is a Roadside Unit (RSU) which uses ITS-G5 protocol to send Infrastructure-to-Vehicle (I2V) messages. The information expected by the vehicle are the recommended path and cone positions to go through the road work area safely. These are transmitted by the RSU to the CAV via DENM and MAPeM, respectively. Layer 3 of HD maps describing roadwork signs is also a descriptor for digital infrastructure in this use case.

The vehicle characteristics descriptors present that the automation level of the ego-vehicle is level 4, i.e. high driving automation. This CAV is a light car equipped with sensors such as front LiDAR and front RADAR. Lane change left maneuver is available for this car, and it can also accelerate or decelerate as its capacity allows.

V. DISCUSSION ABOUT EXODD, AN ESSENTIAL EVOLUTION FOR THE DEPLOYMENT OF CAV

Starting from the ODD constructed with the enhanced taxonomy including PDI and characteristics of the automated ego-vehicle, it is evident that defining a static ODD for a fixed level of vehicle automation poses numerous challenges. The vehicle's characteristics and its ability to operate in an automation mode ranging from level 3 to level 5 are highly dependent on physical infrastructure, environmental conditions, and digital infrastructure. The impact of these different components on the vehicle's operation will be as follows:

- **Physical Infrastructure:** If road markings are unavailable or deteriorated and partially obscured, the automated vehicle's ability to accurately maintain its position in the lane is compromised. The appearance of temporary structures (Road works) will also impact the vehicle's behaviour and potentially create risky and accident-prone situations. This necessitates real-time characterisation and estimation, by section and road segment, of the road's intelligence level to meet the needs of automated vehicles at different levels of automation.
- **Environmental Conditions:** Depending on weather conditions, visibility can be significantly reduced, road markings may become difficult or impossible to perceive, and road surface adhesion may be greatly reduced. All these aspects will impact the capabilities of the automated vehicle, both in terms of its ability to detect obstacles and perceive road markings and vertical signalling. Moreover, the degradation of road surface adhesion will affect the vehicle's tire grip, calling into question safety functions such as emergency braking.
- **Digital Infrastructure:** Disruption of access to digital information from the infrastructure will have a strong impact on predicting and anticipating future risky situations.

Until now, the ODD defined only the operating space

and operational limits of a vehicle, taking into account factors such as static and dynamic road physical infrastructure (without having a real-time impact on the vehicle's behaviour), environmental conditions, and traffic conditions. Standardisation efforts by ASAM and the British standard BSI PAS 1883 have established consistent ODD definitions. However, existing ODD frameworks are static and unsuitable for dynamic road conditions involving the state of the ego-vehicle and interactions between the vehicle and ODD elements. Therefore, it seems important, even essential, to develop a new versatile and real-time adaptive framework to achieve more efficient and based on extended and adaptive definitions of the ODD (ExODD) relying on the updating of enhanced and augmented high-definition map (HD map) attributes, and scores to determine the intelligence class of a road segment and section at any given time (SRC: Smart Road Classification). This type of architecture will offer a comprehensive, cross-cutting, and adaptive solution that will extend and, more importantly, adapt the ODD and, by extension, the authorised level of automation for a vehicle. This extension of the ODD concept will be a crucial safety element in autonomous vehicles. To address this issue, we are currently building a monitoring system that dynamically assesses the ODD, mapping it in real-time using predefined routes, templates, and AI-based models. Continuous validation and monitoring of the current state of the ODD, as suggested by [23][24], offer a pragmatic approach to improving safety. Similarly, [16] introduces an ontology linking ODD, the architecture of automated vehicles, and scenario-based testing. This approach streamlines the development and adaptation process of autonomous driving based on these critical aspects. The use cases of Augmented_CCAM demonstrate the connection between HD maps, PDIs, road environments, and the ODD. Tests cover predefined routes and potentially unknown or temporarily degraded segments, demonstrating the system's adaptability. In conclusion, the development of a dynamic and adaptive ODD system, combined with real-time monitoring of the vehicle and infrastructure's state, is essential for the safe operation of autonomous vehicles in complex road environments. Ensuring the implementation of an ExODD will depend heavily on managing the concepts proposed in Infrastructure Support for Automated Driving (ISAD), Levels of Service for Automated Driving (LOSAD), and SRC. Enhanced HD maps also play a central role in this evolving landscape, facilitating not only navigation but also decision-making for autonomous vehicles. The literature review highlights the need for standardisation and the abundance of HD map creation techniques, both AI-based and traditional. The focus has primarily been on initial layers, unlike the PEGASUS project [25] proposed with six defined layers. To align data from various sources with the current state of an HD map, precise positioning and time-stamping are crucial. Initiatives exist for continuous and high-quality localisation, even in challenging environments for GNSS. Additionally, solutions are under development to manage roadworks and incidents, focusing on communication, AI learning, and distributed and collaborative data processing

Fig. 6. Proposal of the concept of Extended ODD (ExODD) for multiple domains, multiple layers, and adaptive ODD

(crowd-sourcing using vehicles as sensors). In addition to being able to adapt a vehicle's automation level based on ExODD, enhanced HD Map, and the current state of SRC, this data will also be useful for managing preventive maintenance of roads and infrastructure. This service will be essential to ensure the highest SRC, allowing automated vehicles to use the initially defined level of automation with the initial ODD.

VI. CONCLUSION

The presented article introduces a comprehensive taxonomy for Automated Driving Systems (ADS) with a focus on enhancing Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) systems. The taxonomy addresses key aspects such as Operational Design Domain (ODD), Environment Description (ED), Object and Event Detection and Response (OEDR), and Testing scenarios (SCEN). The primary objective is to create a precise and flexible taxonomy tailored to specific activities, allowing for incremental improvements over time. The literature review and existing taxonomy analysis provide a systematic approach to categorizing and evaluating diverse taxonomies found in the literature. The identified taxonomies are classified into four main document types, namely standard-related, institutional-related, research-related, and working group-related documents. The three-tiered tree structure used for analysis involves components, subcategories, and elements, ensuring a cohesive and thorough examination of existing taxonomies. The comparison of existing taxonomies reveals both similarities and differences among them. A notable commonality is the shared foundation on the definition of Operational Design Domain (ODD) as outlined in SAE-J3016. Physical road infrastructure, environmental conditions, and traffic conditions consistently appear in the analyzed taxonomies. Differences include additional ODD components such as subject vehicle, connectivity, other users, and geo-fenced areas, varying across different taxonomies. The proposal of a new taxonomy definition synthesizes insights from the literature review, establishing a foundation for describing the real world precisely and unambiguously. The taxonomy includes components such as physical infrastructure, scenery, environmental conditions, traffic conditions, digital infrastructure, and vehicle features. The two-layer structure of the proposed taxonomy allows for a nuanced representation

of the operational domain. The implementation of the new taxonomy on a specific use case, focusing on Road Workers in the field, demonstrates the practical application of the taxonomy in shaping Operational Design Domain (ODD) descriptors and integrating them into test scenarios. The process involves careful selection of relevant ODD descriptors, considering the specifics of the use case, and then formulating test scenarios based on these descriptors. The presented use case emphasizes the importance of identifying both physical and digital infrastructures (PDIs) during the ODD definition phase and integrating them into test scenarios for a thorough evaluation of autonomous systems. In conclusion, the developed taxonomy and the proposed methodology provide a structured and systematic approach to address the challenges in the field of Automated Driving Systems. The integration of insights from existing taxonomies, the definition of a new taxonomy, and the practical application on a specific use case contribute to advancing the understanding and development of effective and reliable CCAM systems.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Alessandrini, A. Campagna, P. Delle Site, F. Filippi, and L. Persia, "Automated vehicles and the rethinking of mobility and cities," *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol. 5, pp. 145–160, 2015.
- [2] "Taxonomy and definitions for terms related to driving automation systems for on-road motor vehicles (J3016)," Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE), Tech. Rep., 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.4271/J3016.201806>
- [3] C. W. Lee, N. Nayeer, D. E. Garcia, A. Agrawal, and B. Liu, "Identifying the operational design domain for an automated driving system through assessed risk," in *2020 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)*, 2020, pp. 1317–1322.
- [4] L. Mendiboure, M. L. Benzagouta, D. Gruyer, T. Sylla, M. Adedjouma, and A. Hedhli, "Operational design domain for automated driving systems: Taxonomy definition and application," in *2023 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)*, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [5] H. Farah, I. Postigo, N. Reddy, Y. Dong, C. Rydgerren, N. Raju, and J. Olstam, "Modeling automated driving in microscopic traffic simulations for traffic performance evaluations: Aspects to consider and state of the practice," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 6558–6574, 2023.
- [6] "PAS 1883:2020 operational design domain (ODD) taxonomy for an automated driving system (ADS) – Specification," The British Standards Institution (BSI), Tech. Rep., 2020.
- [7] H. Kim, K. Lim, J. Kim, and W. Son, "Operational Design Domain for Testing of Autonomous Shuttle on Arterial Road," *The Journal of The Korea Institute of Intelligent Transport Systems*, vol. 19, pp. 135–148, 2020. [Online]. Available: <http://journal.kits.or.kr/journalarticle.php?code=72004>
- [8] E. Thorn, S. Kimmel, and M. Chaka, "A framework for automated driving system testable cases and scenarios," U.S. Department of Transportation, National Highway Traffic Safety Administration, Tech. Rep. DOT HS 812 623, 2018.
- [9] M. Eddy, M. Mandokhot, and F. Habtemichael, "Collaborative research framework for automated driving system developers and infrastructure owners and operators," U.S. Department of Transportation, Federal Highway Administration, Tech. Rep. FHWA-HOP-21-012, 2021.
- [10] M. Scholtes, L. Westhofen, L. R. Turner, K. Lotto, M. Schuldes, H. Weber, N. Wagener, C. Neurohr, M. H. Bollmann, F. Körtke, J. Hiller, M. Hoss, J. Bock, and L. Eckstein, "6-layer model for a structured description and categorization of urban traffic and environment," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 59 131–59 147, 2021.
- [11] G. Bagschik, T. Menzel, and M. Maurer, "Ontology based scene creation for the development of automated vehicles," in *2018 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)*, 2018, pp. 1813–1820.
- [12] W. Chen and L. Kloul, "An ontology-based approach to generate the advanced driver assistance use cases of highway traffic," in *Proceedings of the 10th International Joint Conference on Knowledge Discovery, Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management (IC3K 2018) - KEOD, INSTICC*. SciTePress, 2018, pp. 75–83.
- [13] J. D. Vreeswijk, A. Wijbenga, and J. Schindler, "Cooperative automated driving for managing transition areas and the operational design domain (ODD)," 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:213511363>
- [14] K. Czarnecki, "Operational design domain for automated driving systems: Taxonomy of basic terms," WISE Requirements Analysis Framework for Automated Driving Systems, Tech. Rep., 2018.
- [15] J. Pfeil, J. Wieland, T. Michalke, and A. Theissler, "On why the system makes the corner case: AI-based holistic anomaly detection for autonomous driving," in *2022 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)*, 2022, pp. 337–344.
- [16] J. Erz, B. Schutt, T. Braun, H. Guissouma, and E. Sax, "Towards an ontology that reconciles the operational design domain, scenario-based testing, and automated vehicle architectures," *IEEE International Systems Conference (SysCon)*, 25-28 April 2022, Montreal, QC, Canada, April 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9773840>
- [17] I. Kim, D. Kang, H. Jeong, S. Lee, and I. Yun, "Method of evaluating multiple scenarios in a single simulation run for automated vehicle assessment," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 19, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/23/19/8271>
- [18] M. Ruchiga, R. Sainct, G. S. Pierre, and D. Gruyer, "Generic ontology and framework for critical scenario description and generation. applied to evaluation and validation of automated vehicle," in *2023 IEEE 26th International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)*, 2023, pp. 783–790.
- [19] M. Gyllenhammar, R. Johansson, F. Warg, D. Chen, and H.-M. Heyn, "Towards an operational design domain that supports the safety argumentation of an automated driving system," in *Proc. 10th Eur. Congr. Embedded Real Time Syst.*, 2020, pp. 1–10. [Online]. Available: <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1390550/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- [20] T. Griffon, J.-L. Sauvaget, S. Geronimi, A. Bolovinou, and R. Brouwer, "Deliverable D4.1: Description and taxonomy of automated driving functions," Groupe PSA, L3Pilot Consortium, Tech. Rep., 2019.
- [21] M. Bach, A. Niemann, and M. Wellens, "OBU requirements - Next generation positioning on board unit," European Global Navigation Satellite Systems Agency (GSA), Tech. Rep., 2021.
- [22] "OpenSCENARIO," Association for Standardization of Automation and Measuring Systems (ASAM), Tech. Rep., 2020.
- [23] C. Sun, Z. Deng, W. Chu, S. Li, and D. Cao, "Acclimatizing the operational design domain for autonomous driving systems," *IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Magazine*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 10–24, April 2022.
- [24] C. Sun, "Operational design domain monitoring and augmentation for autonomous driving," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Waterloo, Ontario, Canada, April 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://uwaterloo.ca/bitstream/handle/10012/18964/Sun.Chen.pdf?sequence=5>
- [25] "Pegasus research project," <https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/about-PEGASUS>, accessed: 2024-02-16.